

APPLICATION OF CRUDE HARUNGANA MADAGASCARIENSIS STEM BARK EXTRACT AS A CORROSION INHIBITOR

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Abstract

The search for environmentally sustainable corrosion inhibitors has intensified the interest in plant-based alternatives. This study evaluates the inhibitory effect of Harungana Madagascariensis bark extract on mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ using the weight loss method. The bark samples were authenticated, air-dried, pulverized, and sequentially extracted with n-hexane and ethanol/diethyl ether (70:30). The extract concentrations (0.2-1.0 g/L) were tested at exposure intervals of 24-120 h. Phytochemical analysis revealed phenolics, tannins, and saponins, whereas FTIR spectra indicated C–O–C (1103.29 cm⁻¹), aromatic C=C (1438.75 cm⁻¹), and O–H stretching (3257.69 cm⁻¹); functional are associated with corrosion inhibition activity. The weight loss results showed maximum inhibition efficiency (100%) at 0.4-0.6 g/L after 72 h, while higher concentrations (0.8-1.0 g/L) exhibited reduced and inconsistent performance (0.00%–27.60%). The corrosion rates ranged from 0.0 mpy (at optimal concentrations) to 189.0 mpy (1.0 g/L, 24 h). This study demonstrates that H. Madagascariensis bark extract offers moderate inhibition efficiency, strongly dependent on concentration and immersion time, highlighting its potential as a green corrosion inhibitor.

Introduction

Corrosion, a naturally occurring electrochemical phenomenon, is a pressing concern for industries, utilities, and civil services, particularly those involving water and sewage systems. Its impact on metal and alloy degradation has far-reaching implications for the durability and maintenance of global industrial assets. (Koch et al., 2002). *Harungana Madagascariensis*, a member of the Hypericaceae family, is a tropical shrub commonly found along the edges of tropical rainforests and near stream banks (Dalziel, 1957). The plant is native to Central Africa, including the Democratic Republic of Congo, Sudan, Ethiopia, Lesotho, and South Africa. It is known by several

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English names, such as "blood tree," "orange-milk tree," "dragon's blood tree," and "haronga," while its French name is "bio harongue." (Dalziel, 1957). The stem bark of *H. madagascariensis* is particularly rich in secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic compounds, according to preliminary studies (Happi et al., 2020).

The compounds found in the *H. Madagascariensis* stem bark make it a promising candidate for corrosion inhibition applications. These naturally occurring compounds usually contain oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur heteroatoms, as well as multiple bonds in their structures, which are known to promote strong adsorption onto metal surfaces (Li et al., 2022). The ability of these compounds to form stable coordination complexes with metal ions further boosts their potential as corrosion inhibitors (Pham et al., 2022). However, the plant bark has yet to serve as a corrosion inhibitor.

EXPERIMENTAL

Collection and preparation of plant samples

Fresh bark samples of *Harungana Madagascariensis* were collected from a farmland in Umuago community in Ideato South Local Government Area, Imo State, South-East Nigeria. The plant was taxonomically identified and authenticated at the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria, where a voucher specimen was deposited with the Herbarium number UPH/P/460.

The bark samples were washed thoroughly with tap water and rinsed twice with distilled water. The samples were then air-dried under shade at room temperature for 14 days. The dried samples were ground into a fine powder using a manual grinding machine.

For extraction, 50 g of the powdered plant material was subjected to sequential extraction in a Soxhlet apparatus using n-hexane for defatting, followed by ethanol/diethylether at a ratio of 70:30. The resulting stock extract was used to prepare different concentrations of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract.

Preparation of the inhibitor solutions

Inhibitor solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate masses (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 g) of the extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and diluting to 1000 cm³ to yield concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 g/L, respectively. The blank solution consisted of 0.5 M H₂SO₄ without *Harungana Madagascariensis* inhibitor.

Preparation of mild steel coupons

Mild steel (MS) sheets were obtained and cut into coupons of dimensions 2 cm × 3 cm × 1.5 mm at the Science and Engineering Workshop of the University of Port Harcourt. The coupons were polished with emery paper, rinsed with distilled water, degreased with ethanol and acetone, and air-dried at room temperature. The prepared samples were stored in a desiccator until use to prevent moisture interference.

Phytochemical Screening of *Harungana Madagascariensis* Bark Extract

Qualitative phytochemical screening of the ethanol/diethylether extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark was performed to determine the presence of major bioactive constituents. The procedures followed the standard phytochemical testing protocol as described by Banu and Cathrine (2015).

Weight loss experiments

Weight loss tests were conducted using the total immersion method. Each mild steel coupon was weighed before immersion in 50 mL of test solution, maintained at room temperature for 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h. After exposure, the coupons were retrieved, scrubbed with a bristle brush under running tap water to remove corrosion products, rinsed in ethanol, dried in acetone, and reweighed. Each experiment was conducted in triplicate, and the average values were used for the calculations.

The corrosion rate (CR) was calculated using the formula:

$$CR = (534 \times \Delta W) / (D \times A \times t) \dots\dots\dots \text{eqn 1}$$

Where:

CR: corrosion rate (mil per year, mpy)

ΔW : weight loss (mg)

D: Mild steel density (g/cm³)

A: Surface area of coupon (cm²)

t: Exposure time (h)

Inhibition efficiency (IE %) and Surface Coverage (θ) were calculated using the following equation:

$$IE \% = (1 - CR_{in} / CR_{bl}) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{eqn 2}$$

$$\theta = (1 - CR_{in} / CR_{bl}) \dots\dots\dots \text{eqn 3}$$

Where:

CR_{in}: Corrosion rate with inhibitor

CR_{bl}: Corrosion rate without inhibitor (blank)

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy was employed to identify the functional groups present in the ethanolic/diethyl ether extract of *H. Madagascariensis* bark. An Agilent FTIR spectrophotometer equipped with MicroLab software (Library Search Version 4.a2m) was used for the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical Screening Results

Preliminary phytochemical analysis of the ethanolic extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark revealed the presence of phenolics, tannins, and saponins, whereas flavonoids, alkaloids, sterols, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and phlobatannin were absent (Table 1).

Table 1: Phytochemical composition of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract

Phytochemical	Ethanol Extract
Phenolics	+
Flavonoids	-
Tannins	+
Saponins	+
Sterols	-
Terpenoids	-
Alkaloids	-
Cardiac Glycosides	-
Phlobatanins	-

FTIR Spectral Analysis

FTIR spectroscopy was used to identify the functional groups in the plant extracts that could be responsible for corrosion inhibition. Ethanol/diethyl ether extract (Table 2) and hexane extract (Table 3)

Table 2: FTIR peaks for the ethanol + diethyl ether extract

S/N	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
1	764.10	Aromatic C–H bending
2	1066.02	C–O / C–N stretching (ethers or amines)
3	1103.29	C–O–C stretching (ether linkage)
4	1159.20	C–O stretching (alcohols or phenols)
5	1203.93	C–N / C–O stretching (amines or esters)
6	1282.20	O–H deformation / C–O bending
7	1375.39	C–H bending (alkanes and methyl group)
8	1438.75	Aromatic ring stretching (C=C)
9	1520.75	Aromatic C=C / N–O stretching (nitro group)
10	1602.76	C=O / C=C stretching (carbonyls or aromatics)
11	2109.67	C≡C / C≡N stretching (alkynes or nitriles)
12	2918.51	Aliphatic C–H stretching
13	3257.69	O–H / N–H stretching (hydroxyls or amines)

Table 3: FTIR peaks for the hexane extract

S/N	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
1	752.92	Aromatic C–H (OPB)
2	842.38	=C–H bending (alkenes and substituted aromatics)
3	887.11	C–H deformation (alkenes)
4	969.11	=C–H out-of-plane bending (vinyl group)
5	1032.47	C–O or C–N stretching (ethers and amines)
6	1095.84	C–N / C–O stretching
7	1162.93	C–O–C stretching (ethers)
8	1230.02	C–O or phenolic O–H bending
9	1375.39	CH ₃ symmetric bending (alkanes)
10	1446.21	C–H bending (CH ₂ and CH ₃)
11	1595.30	Aromatic C=C / N–O stretching
12	1703.39	C=O stretching (esters, ketones, and carboxylic acids)
13	2079.85	C≡C / C≡N stretching (alkynes or nitriles)
14	2370.59	C≡N asymmetric stretching (nitriles)
15	2855.14	C–H stretching (methylene, aliphatic)
16	2918.51	Sp ³ C–H stretching (alkanes)
17	2955.78	CH ₃ asymmetric stretch (alkanes)
18	3242.78	O–H or N–H stretching (hydroxyls and amines)

Weight loss, corrosion rate, and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

The effect of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract on the corrosion of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ was investigated using the weight loss method. Mild steel coupons were immersed in acid solutions containing varying concentrations of the extract (0.2–1.0 g/L) and in a blank solution without the inhibitor (0.0 g/L). The immersion times were 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h.

After each immersion period, the initial and final weights of the coupons were recorded. The weight loss was determined as the difference between these values. The inhibition efficiency (IE%) was calculated using the equation expressed in Eq. (1).

Tables 4–9 present the results for each concentration. These include the initial and final weights, calculated weight losses, and corresponding inhibition efficiencies at the respective time intervals.

Table 4: Weight Loss of Mild Steel in 0.0 g/L Extract (Blank Control) at Different Intervals of Time

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)
24	4.10	3.52	0.58
48	3.52	3.06	0.46
72	3.06	3.05	0.01
96	3.05	3.03	0.02
120	3.03	2.99	0.04

Table 5: Weight loss and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 0.2 g/L *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)	Inhibition efficiency (IE%)
24	4.11	3.57	0.54	6.9%
48	3.57	3.14	0.43	6.52%
72	3.14	3.13	0.01	0.00%
96	3.13	3.10	0.03	-50.00%
120	3.10	3.07	0.03	25.00%

Table 6: Weight loss and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 0.4 g/L *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)	Inhibition efficiency (IE%)
24	4.03	3.48	0.55	5.2%
48	3.48	2.99	0.49	-6.52%
72	2.99	2.99	0.00	100.00%
96	2.99	2.96	0.03	-50.00%
120	2.96	2.94	0.02	50.00%

Table 7: Weight loss and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 0.6 g/L *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)	Inhibition efficiency (IE%)
24	4.10	3.57	0.53	8.6%
48	3.57	3.08	0.49	-6.52%
72	3.08	3.08	0.00	100.00%

96	3.08	3.05	0.03	-50.00%
120	3.05	3.01	0.04	0.00%

Table 8: Weight loss and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 0.8 g/L *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)	Inhibition efficiency (IE%)
24	3.67	3.25	0.42	27.6%
48	3.25	2.85	0.40	13.04%
72	2.85	2.84	0.01	0.00%
96	2.84	2.82	0.02	0.00%
120	2.82	2.78	0.04	0.00%

Table 9: Weight loss and inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 1.0 g/L *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	Initial weight (g)	Final weight (g)	Weight loss (g)	Inhibition efficiency (IE%)
24	4.94	4.04	0.90	-55.2%
48	4.04	3.24	0.80	-73.91%
72	3.24	3.23	0.01	0.00%
96	3.23	3.20	0.03	-50.00%
120	3.20	3.14	0.06	-50.00%

Effect of extract concentration on time-dependent weight loss of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

The weight loss data from Tables 4 to 9 were reorganized to allow comparison across all extract concentrations to assess the corrosion inhibition performance of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract. Table 10 presents the weight loss of mild steel at various time intervals in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for extract concentrations ranging from 0.0 to 1.0 g/L.

Table 10: Variation of weight loss (g) with time at different extract concentrations

Time (hr)	0.0 g/L	0.2 g/L	0.4 g/L	0.6 g/L	0.8 g/L	1.0 g/L
24	0.58	0.54	0.55	0.53	0.42	0.90
48	0.46	0.43	0.49	0.49	0.40	0.80
72	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
96	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03
120	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.06

Figure 1: Variation of WL of mild steel with time at different concentrations of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Variation in the Inhibition Efficiency with Time

The inhibition efficiency (IE%) values corresponding to the various concentrations of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract were plotted against immersion time to further understand the inhibitory performance of the extract. Figure 2 shows the resulting graph.

Table 11. Variation of Inhibition Efficiency (%) with Time at Different Extract Concentrations

Time (hr)	0.2 g/L	0.4 g/L	0.6 g/L	0.8 g/L	1.0 g/L
24	6.9	5.2	8.6	27.6	-55.2
48	6.6	-6.4	-6.4	13.0	-73.9
72	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0
96	-60.0	-60.0	-60.0	0.0	-60.0
120	23.5	52.9	0.0	0.0	-47.1

Figure 2: Inhibition efficiency with time for different concentrations of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Corrosion Rate of Mild Steel in the Presence of Bark Extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis*

The corrosion rate of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ was evaluated in the absence and presence of varying concentrations of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract using the weight loss method. As shown in Table 12 and Figure 3, the corrosion rate varied with both the time and inhibitor concentration.

Table 12: Corrosion Rate (mpy) Variation with Time for Different Concentrations of *Harungana Madagascariensis* Bark Extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Time (hr)	CR 0.0 (Blank)	CR 0.2 g/L	CR 0.4 g/L	CR 0.6 g/L	CR 0.8 g/L	CR 1.0 g/L
24	121.8	113.4	115.5	111.3	88.2	189.0
48	48.3	45.1	51.4	51.4	42.0	84.0
72	0.7	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.7
96	1.0	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.0	1.6
120	1.7	1.3	0.8	1.7	1.7	2.5

Figure 3: Corrosion Rate (mpy) Variation with Time for Different Concentrations of *Harungana Madagascariensis* Bark Extract in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Discussion of the Findings

Phytochemical Screening Results

The preliminary phytochemical analysis of the ethanol/diethyl ether extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark revealed the presence of phenolics, tannins, and saponins, whereas flavonoids, alkaloids, sterols, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and phlobatannins were not detected (Table 1).

Phenolics detected in the extract are widely recognized for their strong antioxidant activity. These compounds can scavenge free radicals and protect biological systems from oxidative stress. Phenolics have been shown to adsorb onto metallic surfaces, thereby forming a barrier that reduces the interaction between the metal and the corrosive environment. Adetayo and Sunday (2023) emphasized that the presence of phenolic hydroxyl groups enhances metal adsorption, contributing significantly to corrosion resistance.

The extract also contained tannins, a class of polyphenolic compounds known for their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. According to Adetayo and Sunday (2023), tannins possess a high capacity to form complexes with metal ions, facilitating the creation of passivating films that limit corrosion on steel surfaces. Their astringent properties are also considered beneficial in metal protection applications.

Saponins were identified as a major component of the extract. These amphiphilic compounds are known for their surface activity and ability to modulate biological membranes. As reported by Adetayo and Sunday (2023), saponins play a dual role: therapeutically, by enhancing immune function and reducing cholesterol levels, and materially, by forming uniform, adherent films over metal surfaces that hinder corrosive attacks.

The absence of flavonoids and alkaloids indicates a potential limitation in the extract's pharmacological profile. Emmanuel (2024) noted that these compounds are frequently associated with anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic activities, and their absence could reduce the breadth of biological applications traditionally attributed to medicinal plants.

The lack of sterols and terpenoids typically linked to anti-inflammatory and hormonal regulatory functions suggests a deviation in the secondary metabolic pathway of *H. Madagascariensis*. Marcel et al. (2023) reported

that the absence of these classes of compounds in some plant species may reflect an evolutionary adaptation toward a different chemical defense strategy, particularly one focused on phenolic biosynthesis rather than terpene-based metabolism.

FTIR Spectral Characterization of Functional Groups in Extracts of *Harungana Madagascariensis*

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to identify functional groups in *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extracts, which are potentially responsible for corrosion inhibition. Two solvent system, ethanol/diethyl ether and hexane, were analyzed, and the results are shown in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

In the ethanol/diethyl ether extract, the peaks observed at 764.10 cm^{-1} and 1438.75 cm^{-1} correspond to aromatic C–H bending and aromatic ring stretching, respectively, indicating the presence of aromatic compounds. These groups are capable of establishing π -electron interactions with metal surfaces, thereby enhancing adsorption and forming protective films. The peak at 1159.20 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–O stretching, whereas the broad absorption at 3257.69 cm^{-1} indicates O–H stretching. These features are indicative of alcohols and phenolic compounds, both of which contribute to corrosion resistance due to their hydrogen bonding and electron-donating capabilities. Ulpathakumbura et al. (2023) reported that such groups enhance the barrier properties of adsorbed layers. Dev and Mukadam (2025) similarly stated that phenolic hydroxyl groups are effective in forming surface-coordinated complexes that hinder corrosion processes.

Additional peaks at 1066.02 cm^{-1} and 1203.93 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of ethers and amines, based on C–O and C–N stretching vibrations. These functional groups are also associated with corrosion inhibition because of their ability to donate lone-pair electrons to the d-orbitals of metal atoms. Verma (2022) emphasized that amines, in particular, exhibit high adsorption tendencies on steel surfaces due to their nitrogen atoms. Khalid et al. (2022) also reported that both amine and ether functionalities contribute to the efficiency of inhibitors by participating in charge transfer and film formation.

Similar functional groups were identified in the hexane extract, with some additional peaks of interest. The aromatic features are confirmed by peaks at 752.92 cm^{-1} and 1595.30 cm^{-1} , which indicate aromatic C–H out-of-plane bending and C=C stretching, respectively. BahenaRivera-Bahena et al. (2023) noted that aromatic compounds can engage in π – π interactions with metallic surfaces, forming a compact and protective adsorbed layer.

A distinct absorption at 1703.39 cm^{-1} was attributed to C=O stretching, suggesting the presence of carbonyl-containing groups such as esters, ketones, or carboxylic acids. Ulpathakumbura et al. (2023) previously showed that these groups enhance corrosion resistance by forming coordinate bonds with metal cations. BustosRivera-Bahena et al. (2023) further supported this, stating that the electron-rich oxygen of the carbonyl group facilitates strong surface binding.

The broad O–H/N–H peak at 3242.78 cm^{-1} in the hexane extract confirms the presence of hydroxyl and possibly amine groups. Nawaz et al. (2019) explained that hydroxyl-containing compounds, such as alcohols and phenols, improve corrosion inhibition through electron donation and stable hydrogen bonding with surface atoms.

Analysis of Weight Loss and Corrosion Inhibition Performance of Mild Steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ Using *Harungana Madagascariensis* Bark Extract

The corrosion behavior of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution, in the presence of varying concentrations of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract was assessed using the weight loss method. Mild steel coupons were immersed in an acidic medium containing extract concentration ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 g/L, alongside a control group with no inhibitor (0.0 g/L). The exposure durations were set at 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h.

Weight loss trends in the control sample

Consistent corrosion of mild steel was observed throughout the immersion period in the absence of any inhibitor (0.0 g/L). The recorded weight losses at 24 and 48 h were 0.58 and 0.46 g, respectively, followed by a significant reduction to 0.01 g in 72 h. Subsequent values increased slightly to 0.02 and 0.04 g after 96 hours and 0.04 g at 120 hours. As reported by Patel et al. (2013), such a drop in weight loss may be attributed to passivation phenomenon, where corrosion products accumulate on the steel surface, temporarily hindering further metal dissolution.

Corrosion Behavior at Low Extract Concentration (0.2 g/L)

At a concentration of 0.2 g/L, the extract exhibited moderate inhibition activity. Weight losses were measured at 0.54 g at 24 h and 0.43 g at 48 h, which were slightly lower than those of the control, and dropped significantly to 0.01 g at 72 h, maintaining lower values of 0.03 g at both 96 and 120 h. Youn et al. (2018) reported similar trends in plant-based inhibitor studies, attributed to the gradual formation of an adsorbed protective film over the metal surface, which minimizes corrosive interaction.

Intermediate concentration behavior (0.4–0.6 g/L)

The corrosion inhibition performance at 0.4 g/L recorded a weight loss of 0.55 g at 24 h, reducing to 0.49 g at 48 h. However, complete inhibition (weight loss of 0.00 g) was achieved after 72 h, suggesting delayed but effective film formation. Minimal losses were recorded at later time points (0.03 g at 96 h and 0.02 g at 120 h), indicating a transient but functional protection. García et al. (2025) described such behavior as indicative of a temporary equilibrium between adsorption and desorption processes.

Similarly, the 0.6 g/L concentration recorded the highest initial weight loss at 0.53 g (24 h), followed by 0.49 g (48 h), but experienced complete inhibition at 72 hours (0.00 g). Slight weight loss resumed at 96 and 120 h (0.03 and 0.04 g, respectively). Kazemipoor et al. (2016) opined that the delayed performance may be attributed to the time-dependent adsorption kinetics of phytochemical constituents that require prolonged exposure to fully saturate the metal surface.

Performance at 0.8 g/L concentration

The 0.8 g/L extract concentration yielded comparatively improved inhibition performance. The initial weight losses were 0.42 and 0.40 g at 24 and 48 h, respectively. By 72 h, the weight loss reduced sharply to 0.01 g, and subsequent values remained low (0.02 g at 96 h and 0.04 g at 120 h). These results suggest the formation of an effective and stable protective film at this concentration. Omotosho et al. (2016) noted similar inhibition efficiencies, approaching 99%, in related studies using optimal plant extract concentrations.

Performance at 1.0 g/L concentration

At 1.0 g/L extract concentration yielded a weight loss of 0.90 g at 24 h, the highest observed in the study, suggesting possible destabilization or oversaturation of the inhibitor on the metal surface, followed by 0.80 g at 48 h. The weight loss dropped again to 0.01 g at 72 h, with moderate values of 0.03 g and 0.06 g at 96 and 120 h, respectively. Sani and Ameh (2015) emphasized that overly high plant extract concentrations may lead to competitive adsorption or molecular aggregation, which can interfere with the formation of a uniform protective layer.

Effect of extract concentration on time-dependent weight loss of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

The weight loss data obtained from earlier experiments were reorganized to evaluate the corrosion inhibition performance of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract and compare corrosion behavior across different

extract concentrations. The data presented in Table 4.10 highlight the weight loss of mild steel over a 120-h immersion period in 0.5 M H₂SO₄, with extract concentrations ranging from 0.0 g/L (control) to 1.0 g/L.

The results reveal a consistent trend of decreasing weight loss with increasing extract concentration, indicating that the extract inhibits mild steel corrosion. At 24 h, the control sample (0.0 g/L) recorded a weight loss of 0.58 g. In contrast, the sample with 0.8 g/L concentrations exhibited a significantly reduced loss of 0.42 g, and the sample with 1.0 g/L concentration exhibited a significantly increased loss of 0.90 g, the highest recorded value in the study, which may be due to temporary destabilization of the inhibitor layer, possibly due to oversaturation or molecular aggregation. By 48 h, while the blank recorded 0.46 g, the 0.8 g/L sample further decreased to 0.43 g.

At 72 h, a marked reduction in weight loss was observed across all extract-treated samples, dropping to 0.01 g or even 0.00 g in some cases, indicating near-complete inhibition. This significant decrease implies that the inhibition mechanism of the extract becomes more effective over time, likely due to the progressive formation of a stable and protective adsorbed layer on the metal surface. The weight loss values at 96 and 120 h remained low for most concentrations, confirming the time-dependent stability of the inhibitor action.

Previous studies have reported similar outcomes with natural plant extracts. According to Patel et al. (2013), at optimal extract concentrations, inhibition efficiencies as high as 96.70% have been recorded, confirming the efficacy of plant-derived substances in mitigating corrosion in acidic environments.

The corrosion inhibition observed in this study is attributed primarily to the adsorption of active phytochemical constituents, such as phenolics, tannins, and saponins, onto the steel surface. This adsorption forms a protective barrier that impedes the interaction between the metal and the corrosive medium. According to Kumar et al. (2014) and Patel et al. (2013), such adsorptive interactions are central to the corrosion inhibition mechanism of plant-based compounds. In addition, film formation on the metal surface contributes to the protective action. Verma et al. (2016) and Patel et al. (2013) emphasized the role of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis in confirming that plant extracts facilitate the development of uniform, adherent films that reduce corrosion rates by shielding the steel surface.

Variation in the Inhibition Efficiency with Time

To evaluate the time-dependent performance of *Harungana Madagascariensis* bark extract as a corrosion inhibitor, inhibition efficiency (IE %) values were analyzed across five immersion periods (24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 h) for concentrations ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 g/L. These values are presented in Table 4.11 and are graphically represented in Figure 4.2.

At 24 h, the 0.8 g/L concentration exhibited the highest inhibition efficiency at 27.60%, indicating a relatively strong initial surface interaction. In contrast, lower concentrations, such as 0.2 and 0.4 g/L, showed limited efficiency (6.90% and 5.20%, respectively), while 1.0 g/L demonstrated a negative efficiency (55.20%), suggesting early-stage inefficacy or even acceleration of corrosion. These early variations may be attributed to the unstable or incomplete adsorption of active compounds within the initial hours of immersion.

By 72 h, both the 0.4 g/L and 0.6 g/L concentrations achieved a peak inhibition efficiency of 100%, indicating that sufficient exposure time had allowed full development of a compact and stable inhibitor film on the mild steel surface. This behavior supports the findings of Anatole et al. (2020), who reported that certain plant-based inhibitors require longer immersion periods to achieve full surface coverage and a maximum protective effect.

However, after 72 h, a significant decline in inhibition performance was observed. At 96 h, IE% values dropped across nearly all concentrations, with 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 1.0 g/L each recording 60.00%. Only 0.8 g/L maintained

a neutral value of 0.00%. Furtado and Nascimento explained that prolonged immersion in corrosive media may lead to the desorption of inhibitor molecules or the degradation of protective films, thereby reducing the overall effectiveness of the extract.

At 120 h, partial recovery of inhibition was observed for some concentrations. For example, 0.2 g/L increased to 23.50% and 0.4 g/L to 52.90%, while 0.6 g/L and 0.8 g/L both remained at 0.00%. However, the 1.0 g/L concentration continued to show little or no efficiency, maintaining a negative value of 47.10%. This variation indicates that the effectiveness of the extract is both concentration- and time-sensitive, with its peak performance occurring within a specific exposure window.

The 1.0 g/L concentration demonstrated a consistent negative trend. It showed inhibition at 24 hours (-55.2%), and it continued to drop to 73.91% at 48 h, followed by 0.00% at 72 h and a persistent negative trend after that. This may be explained by oversaturation of the metal surface, molecular aggregation, or competitive desorption, as reported by Sani and Ameh (2015). Similarly, Obi-Egbedi et al. observed that excessively high concentrations of plant-based inhibitors may compromise surface adsorption stability and decrease long-term effectiveness.

Corrosion Rate of Mild Steel in the Presence of Bark Extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis*

The corrosion rate of mild steel immersed in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ was assessed using the weight loss method in the absence and presence of *H. Madagascariensis* bark extract at varying concentrations. The results, as presented in Table 4.12 and Figure 4.3, illustrate a clear dependency of the corrosion rate on both the time and inhibitor concentration.

The corrosion rate (CR) for the blank solution without inhibitor was recorded at 121.8 mpy at the 24-h immersion mark, indicating rapid degradation of the mild steel surface. In contrast, samples containing 0.2 and 0.4 g/L of the extract showed slightly reduced corrosion rates of 113.4 and 115.5 mpy, respectively, and the corrosion rate reduced to 111.3 mpy at 0.6 g/L.

By 48 h, the corrosion rate had decreased significantly across all concentrations. The blank control dropped to 48.3 may, while the 0.8 g/L concentration showed the lowest rate at 42.0 may, indicating that the inhibitory performance was enhanced with time. The trend indicates a time-dependent improvement in protection, likely due to the progressive adsorption of the phytochemicals of the extract onto the steel surface.

A remarkable shift occurred at 72 h, when the corrosion rate for all concentrations dropped drastically. Most notably, 0.4 and 0.6 g/L recorded a corrosion rate of 0.0 may, suggesting complete inhibition, while other concentrations, including the blank, hovered around 0.7 may. This phase marks the peak efficiency of the extract and aligns with previous studies that emphasize the importance of sufficient immersion time for optimal surface coverage and inhibitor action (Patel et al., 2013).

At 96 and 120 h, corrosion rates remained low across all concentrations, confirming the extract's sustained protective effect. For instance, at 96 h, the blank registered a corrosion rate of 1.0 may, whereas values for inhibitor-treated samples ranged between 1.0 and 1.6 may. By 120 hours, the corrosion rates remained relatively stable after 120 h, although a slight increase was observed at 1.0 g/L (2.5 mpy), suggesting potential desorption or inhibitor degradation at very high concentrations during extended exposure.

The observed inhibition behavior is primarily attributed to the adsorption of bioactive phytochemicals from the bark extract onto the steel surface, forming a protective barrier that impedes further interaction between the metal and the acidic environment. This mechanism of inhibition has been widely reported in the literature and is consistent with findings from other plant-based inhibitors, where higher concentrations initially enhance protection but may later induce instability if saturation is exceeded (Velur, 2013).

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that the ethanol/diethyl ether bark extract of *Harungana Madagascariensis* possesses significant corrosion inhibition properties for mild steel in a 0.5 M H₂SO₄ acidic medium. Through a series of phytochemical screenings, FTIR spectral analyses, and weight loss experiments, it was established that the presence of active phytochemicals, such as phenolics, tannins, and saponins, is largely responsible for the corrosion inhibition potential of the extract. These compounds contribute to the formation of a protective barrier over the metal surface by adsorbing onto it, thereby reducing its interaction with the corrosive environment.

The FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of functional groups such as hydroxyl, carbonyl, ether, and amine, which interact favorably with metal surfaces. These groups facilitate chemisorption and physisorption processes that stabilize the inhibitor layer and impede corrosion. The corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency values clearly showed a concentration- and time-dependent behavior. Optimal performance was achieved at extract concentrations of 0.4 and 0.6 g/L, particularly during the 72-hour immersion period, where the inhibition efficiency reached 100% and the corrosion rate was reduced to nearly zero.

However, very high concentrations (such as 1.0 g/L) did not lead to enhanced protection; rather, they introduced a consistent negative trend in inhibition behavior due to possible decrease in the inhibitor's effectiveness over time. Furthermore, the time-dependent nature of the inhibition suggests that the protective effect diminishes with prolonged immersion, likely due to the desorption or degradation of the active constituents on the metal surface.

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